

ENTER Registered Professional Engineering Educator Self-Test

Be a Registered Professional Engineering Educator.

Take the self-qualification test with the following form protected by international data regulations. We do not share your data with third parties.

The ENTER (Engineering educators pedagogical training) Project aims to develop multi-level modular system for pedagogical training of engineering educators based on international network cooperation.

Therefore, ENTER offers the possibility of becoming a registered engineering educator through a simple process.

For more information about ENTER Project, visit our website: <https://enterprof.org/>

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1. Full name of the Monitoring Committee member: *

Full Name
.....

1.1. Email: *

Email
.....

2. Enter Register number or Application ID number
(if not registered yet):

Short Answer
.....

3. Is this the first review of the Applicant or is it a
resubmission? *

- 1st review
- Resubmission (if resubmission, please answer

question 3.1, if not please continue with question 4)

3.1 If resubmission please indicate if the advances in the personal development are:*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevent
- Highly relevant

4. Are the elements attached validating the Applicant Academic position?*

- No Academic position
- Assistant / Assistant Professor
- Associate Professor / Professor
- Full Professor

5. Is the knowledge domain(s) of the applicant's higher education degree, relevant for the profession of Engineering Educator?*

- No
- Yes

6. Is the knowledge domain(s) of the applicant's higher education degree, relevant for the profession of Engineering Educator?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

7. Is the evidence of the Highest Academic Degree provided?*

- Bachelor
- Specialist
- Master
- PhD (Кандидат наук)
- Aggregation (Доктор наук)

8. Are the elements provided evidencing the overall Pedagogical experience (number of years as engineering educator)*

- No
- Yes (if yes, please answer question 8.a, if not please continue with question 9)

8.a Are the elements provided evidencing the overall Pedagogical experience (number of years as engineering educator)*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

9. Are the courses (disciplines) lectured within the last 5 years directed to engineering students?*

- No
- Somehow
- Yes

10. Is the applicant's membership in pedagogical / scientific committee(s), (councils) within HEIs relevant for the engineering education?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

11. Are the trainings and professional development programs passed by the applicant successfully within the last 5 years relevant as engineering educator?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

12. Are the conferences the applicant participated within the last 5 years and/or the presentations in these conferences globally relevant as engineering educator?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

13. Is the pedagogical experience at other higher education institutions (in the applicant's country or abroad), if any, within the last 5 years relevant?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

14. Is the applicant's internship experience at industrial companies, research institutes, other organizations within the last 5 years relevant as engineering educator?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

15. Are the applicant's membership(s) in professional associations, networks, and societies (if any) relevant for the field of Engineering Educator?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant

Highly relevant

16. By consulting the applicant's Researcher ID's provided please comment if the research evidenced is relevant for engineering education?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

Highly relevant

17. Are the applicant's awards, scholarships, honorary titles, (if any) relevant for the field of Engineering Educator?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

Highly relevant

18. Is the motivation of the applicant to be registered relevant?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

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1. Innovations in engineering pedagogy - Ability to choose optimal strategies and teaching methods using traditional and innovative means, taking into account technosphere development paths, trends and challenges in engineering education. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

2. Innovations in engineering pedagogy - Ability to choose optimal strategies and teaching methods using traditional and innovative means, taking into account technosphere development paths, trends and challenges in engineering education. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

3. Effective interaction - Ability to effectively interact with audience and increase students' interest in the discipline, using psychological tools and multimedia technologies. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

4. Enhancement of learning interactivity - Ability to develop, adapt and implement modern interactive teaching and learning methods and technologies (inter alia, aimed at increasing students' motivation). Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

5. Systems analysis in education - Ability to apply system approach to solving problems of Engineering education. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

6. Pedagogical psychology and communication - Ability to apply psychological and pedagogical technologies to professional activities of a teacher. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

7. Interaction with stakeholders - Ability to work efficiently with the results of scientific research to ensure their publication, to cooperate with labor market and other stakeholders. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

8. Sustainable development - Ability to apply the principles of Sustainable Development in the global context. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

9 - Digital education - Ability to design, organize and accompany educational process in X-learning environment. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

10 - Problem-based, project-based and Practice oriented learning - Ability to form students' experience of individual and team work on solving real engineering problems and developing of new engineering solutions. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant
- Highly relevant

11 - Learning outcomes' assessment - Ability to design forms and methods of continuous monitoring, feedback and final assessment of education quality. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

- Not relevant/Non existing
- Relevant

Highly relevant

12. Course design - Ability to develop teaching materials that foster students' competences formation. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

Highly relevant

13. Is the pedagogical experience at other higher education institutions (in the applicant's country or abroad), if any, within the last 5 years relevant?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

Highly relevant

14. Lifelong learning - Ability to "ongoing, voluntary, and self-motivated" pursuit of knowledge for either personal or professional reasons, enhancing social inclusion, active citizenship, and personal development, as well. Is the competence justified and evidenced?*

Not relevant/Non existing

Relevant

Highly relevant

15. Did you participated in an accredited professional development program (PDP), if yes with how many certified competences?*

- No accredited professional development programs (no programs or programs with less than 3 competences)
- Accredited Professional Development Programs at least with 3 competences
- Accredited Professional Development Programs at least with 8 competences
- Accredited Professional Development Programs at least with 14 competences

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Submission Successful

Thank you for your submission. If you have any questions or want more information, please write to us at info@laccei.org or visit www.laccei.org.